

The Petite Cour in marble

It is made up of two large oblong rooms which revolve around an interior patio entirely paved with zellige and marble with a basin superbly located in the centre.

The ornamentation consists of cedar wood ceilings, doors and leaves painted with floral, geometric and epigraphic motifs.

This pavilion served as a private residence for Ba Hmad and, under the French Protectorate, while hosting the military mission under Marshal Lyautey, it was known as the “Military Pavilion”.